

Pap Smear: A Screening Test for Cervical Cancer

Rabia Bint-e- Iftikhar¹, Saniya Ahmed¹, Bilquis Begum²

¹ 4th year Medical Student, Rawalpindi Medical University.

² Assistant Professor, Pathology Department, Holy Family Hospital, Rawalpindi.

Abstract:

Background: Cervical cancer is one of the leading causes of mortality and morbidity in women worldwide. This can be detected effectively in pre invasive forms by using certain screening tests among which the Pap smear test is most widely used. This study was conducted to determine the frequency of abnormal cervical cytology by Pap smear and to stress upon the role of Pap smear in screening of cervical cancer.

Materials & Methods: A cross sectional descriptive study was carried out on 121 patients, reporting to a private lab, selected through non probability convenience sampling technique. Patients with complete referral forms were included and then their lab reports were reviewed. The required data (including slide number, age, reason of referral and lab findings) was collected on a Proforma and was further analyzed by SPSS version 23. By using descriptive statistics, frequencies were calculated and cross tabulations were made.

Results: Out of 121 lab reports, 57%(n=69) were normal, 34.7%(n=42) had inflammation without atypia, 1.7%(n=2) had Inflammation with atypia, 2.5%(n=3) had ASCUS, 1.7%(n=2) had LSIL, 1.7%(n=2) had HSIL and 0.8%(n=1) had cervical cancer. On total,

8.4%(n=10) reports were having abnormal cervical cytologies including one case (0.8%) of Invasive cervical carcinoma. 7.6% cases were found to be potentially pre invasive (i.e. Atypia , ASCUS , LSIL , HSIL). Out of which 66% were found in the age group of above 40 years.

Conclusion: Pap test effectively picked up 7.6% cases of abnormal cervical epithelium in potentially pre invasive forms. 66% of these cases were found in the age group of above 40 years.

Key words: Cervical cancer, Pap smear test, screening test

Introduction:

Worldwide, cervical cancer is rated as the third most frequent cancer in women and seventh most frequent

cancer in general population with high morbidity and mortality rates.¹ In the year 2012, 527,624 new cases and 265,672 deaths were recorded all over the world. In Pakistan, it ranks as third leading cause of cancer in women with annual 5,233 new cases and 2,876 deaths.² It progresses very slowly in about 10-15 years from pre-invasive to invasive form.^{1,3} Pre-invasive forms can be effectively detected beforehand by using appropriate laboratory tests.³ No other cancer can be screened out and cured so effectively as does the cervical cancer.¹ Cervical cancer screening can be done via two tests; Cytology based pap smear test and HPV testing.⁴ Pap test is the most commonly applied screening test to identify pre-invasive forms and thus contributing in reducing the incidence of cervical carcinoma and mortality caused by it.⁵

People in Pakistan have got very scarce knowledge regarding these screening tests. Moreover, these facilities are not available in all parts of the country. Cervical cancer screening coverage is just 2.3 %.² As per a KAP survey conducted in Lahore, only 5% of females were found to be aware of screening and among them 2.6% had a screening test done once in life. Routine Pap test is not practiced in gynecological clinics and hospitals.^{6,7}

This study is aimed to determine the frequency of abnormal cervical cytology by Pap smear and to stress upon the role of Pap smear test in screening of cervical cancers. Moreover, results of this research will be helpful at the level of policy making too.

Materials and Methods:

This cross sectional descriptive study was done in a private laboratory of Rawalpindi to analyze the previously conducted cervical Pap smears during the period of 2008-2017. After excluding the referral forms with inadequate data, 121 patients were selected on the basis of non-probability convenience sampling and their laboratory reports were reviewed. Information regarding slide no., age, reason of referral and laboratory findings were recorded on a proforma.

Reports of conventional Pap test were considered. The Lab reports were classified by the pathologist using The Bethesda System 2001 of classification for cervical cytology, description of which is as follows:

1. Negative for intraepithelial lesion or malignancy (NIL)(showing organisms or other non-neoplastic changes e.g. Inflammation)
2. Epithelial cell abnormalities
 - A) Atypical squamous cells of undetermined significance (ASCUS) & Atypical Glandular cells of undetermined significance (AGUS).
 - B) Low grade intra-epithelial lesion (LSIL)
 - C) High grade intra-epithelial lesion (HSIL)
 - D) Cervical Carcinoma (Squamous cell carcinoma & Adenocarcinoma)

Data was analyzed by using Statistical Packages for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 23. Frequencies were calculated and cross tabulations were made using the descriptive statistics.

Results:

A total of 121 Lab reports were included in the study. Reasons of referral along with their frequencies are given in Table I.

Lab reports of the Pap smear were reviewed that revealed the results tabulated in Table II.

Patients were divided into two age groups i.e. less than 40 and greater than 40. Among them 59.5 % (n=72) were less than 40 years and 40.5 % (n=49) were greater than 40 years of age. On developing the relation between the two age groups and abnormal cervical cytologist in potentially pre-invasive forms, 66 % (n=06) of them were picked up in women greater than 40 years of age group (p=0.203).

Table I: Reasons of Referral

Reason of Referral	Frequency (n=121)	Percentage
PV Discharge	57	47.1
Post-Menopausal Bleeding	10	8.3
Lower Abdominal Pain	11	9.1
Intermittent Bleeding	21	17.4
Post Coital Bleeding	11	9.1
Dyspareunia	2	1.7
Hypertrophied Cervix	1	0.8
Oligomenorrhea	3	2.5
Menorrhagia	5	4.1

Table II Frequency of Lab Findings of Pap smear

Laboratory Findings		Frequency (n=121)	Percentage
1.	Normal	69	57
2.	Negative For Intraepithelial Lesion		
	-Inflammation Without Atypia.	42	34.7
3.	Abnormal Cervical Epithelium (Preinvasive)		
	-Inflammation With Atypia	2	1.7
	-Ascus*	3	2.5
	-Lsil**	2	1.7
	-Hsil***	2	1.7
4.	Invasive Cervical Cancer	1	0.8

*Atypical squamous cells of undetermined significance.

**Low grade squamous intraepithelial lesion.

***High grade squamous intraepithelial lesion.

Discussion:

This study was conducted in order to determine the frequency of abnormal cervical cytologies in potentially pre-invasive forms by using Pap smear. Current study picked up 8.4% of the abnormal cervical cytologies including 0.8% of invasive cervical cancer as compared to a local study conducted in Swat with the result of 3.76 %⁽⁸⁾. An international study conducted in Saudi Arabia showed 9.2% of abnormal cervical cytologies that is in coherence with the current study⁽⁹⁾. Another study from India was concluded with 3.6% of the results⁽¹⁰⁾.

There is literal evidence of the fact that most of the cervical epithelial abnormalities are asymptomatic unless they progress to the full blown form of cervical cancer. This progression takes a period of 10-15 years. Though current study was conducted on those patients who presented with some symptoms and picked up a total of 8.4% of abnormal cervical cytologies, there are big numbers of cases of abnormal cervical epithelia that go unnoticed. Multiple reasons address this issue, including their asymptomatic pattern, no proper screening system in Pakistan and lack of knowledge among women and health care providers regarding the importance of screening. First and foremost recommendation for the above mentioned issue is that the cervical cancer screening should be one of the governments funded screening programmes. Moreover, this programme should be designed on WHO's recommended pattern i.e. 3 yearly pap smear screening test followed by HPV testing in the age group of 21-29years and 5 yearly

pap smear screening test combined with HPV testing in the age group of 30-65 years. Secondly, women and health care providers should be equipped with the knowledge about the importance of screening via print media, electronic media, seminars and CME workshops.

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